

Optimization of Remote Core Locking Synchronization in Multithreaded Programs for Multicore Computer Systems

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Abstract—This paper proposes the algorithms for optimization of Remote Core Locking (RCL) synchronization method in multithreaded programs. The algorithm of initialization of RCL-locks and the algorithms for threads affinity optimization are developed. The algorithms consider the structures of hierarchical computer systems and non-uniform memory access (NUMA) to minimize execution time of RCL-programs. The experimental results on multi-core computer systems represented in the paper shows the reduction of RCL-programs execution time.

Keywords—remote core locking; RCL; synchronization; critical sections; scalability

I. INTRODUCTION

Currently distributed computer systems (CS) [1] are large-scale and include multiple architectures. These systems are composed of shared memory multi-core compute nodes (SMP, NUMA systems) equipped by universal processors as well as specialized accelerators (graphical processors, massively parallel multi-core processors). The number of processor cores exceeds 10^2 - 10^3 . Effective parallel programs execution on these systems is significant challenge. System software must consider the large scale, multiple architectures and hierarchical structure.

Parallel programs for multi-core CS with shared memory are multithreaded in most cases. The software tools must ensure linear speedup with a large amount of parallel threads. Thread synchronization while accessing to shared data structures is one of the most significant problem of the development of multithreaded programs. The existing approaches for thread synchronization include locks, lock-free algorithms and concurrent data structures [2] and software transactional memory [3].

The main drawback of lock-free algorithms and concurrent data structures despite of their good scalability is the limited application scope and severe complexity related to the parallel programs development [2,4,5]. Furthermore the development of lock-free algorithms and data structures includes the

[6,7], poor performance and restricted nature of atomic operations. Moreover throughput of lock-free concurrent data structures is often similar to corresponding lock-based data structures.

Software transactional memory nowadays have a variety of issues, connected with large overheads when transactions execution and multiple transactions aborts. Moreover the existing transactional memory implementations restricts the operations set inside the transactional section. Consequently transactional memory does not ensure sufficient performance of multithreaded programs and is not applied in common real applications for now.

Conventional approach for synchronization in multithreaded programs by lock-based critical sections is still the most widespread in software development. Locks are simple in usage (comparing with lock-free algorithms and data structures) and in most cases ensure the acceptable performance. Furthermore the most of existing multithreaded programs utilizes lock-based approach. Thereby scalable algorithms and software tools for lock-based synchronization is very important today.

Lock scalability heavily depends on resolutions of the problems, connected with access contention of threads handling with shared memory areas and locality of references. Access contention arises when multiple threads simultaneously access to a critical section, protected by one synchronization primitive. In the terms of hardware it leads to the huge load to the data bus and cache memory inefficiency. The cache memory locality is meaningful when a thread inside critical section access to the shared data previously used on an other processor core. This case leads to the cache misses and significant increase of time of critical section execution.

The main approaches for scalable lock implementations are CAS spinlocks [8], MCS-locks [9], Flat combining [10], CC-Synch [11], DSM-Synch [11], Oyama lock [12].

For the analysis of existing approaches we have to consider the critical section's execution time. Time t of critical section execution comprises the time t_1 critical section's instructions execution and the time t_2 of transfer of lock ownership (Fig. 1). In the existing lock algorithms time of transfer of lock ownership is determined by global flag access

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(CAS spinlocks), context switches and awakening of the thread executing the critical section (PThread mutex, MCS-locks, etc), global lock capture (Flat Combining). Time of critical section's instruction execution time substantially depends on the time t_3 of global variables access. The most existing locking algorithms does not localize access to shared memory areas.

Fig 1. Critical path of critical sections execution.

The existing works includes the methods for localization access to cache memory [10, 13-15]. The works [14, 15] are devoted to concurrent data structures development (lists and hash tables) on the basis of critical section execution on dedicated processor cores. The paper [13] propose universal hardware solution, which includes the set of processor instructions for transferring the ownership to a dedicated processor core. Flat Combining [10] refers to software approaches. Flat Combining suggests the server threads (all the threads become server threads by order), which execute critical sections. But the transfer of lock server ownership between the threads executing on different processor cores leads to performance decrease even at insignificant access contention. Besides that all these algorithms do not support thread locking inside critical sections, including active waiting and operation system core locking.

The ownership transfer involves the overheads due to context switches, global variable cache loading from RAM and activation of the thread executing critical section. Critical section execution time heavily depends on global variables reference localization. Common mutual excluding algorithms assumes frequent context switches, which leads to shared variables extrusion from cache memory.

This paper considers Remote Core Locking (RCL) method [16,17], which assumes execution of critical section on the dedicated processor cores. RCL minimizes execution time of existing programs thanks to critical path reduction (Fig. 2). This technique assumes replacement of high-load critical sections in existing multithreading applications to remote functions calls for its execution on dedicated processor cores (Fig. 2). In this case all the critical sections protected by one lock are executed by server thread running on the dedicated processor core. In this way all critical sections are executed on the particular thread and the overheads of transfer of lock ownership are negligible. RCL also reduces critical sections'

instructions execution time. That is reached by localizing the data, protected by particular lock, in the cache memory, which is local for the RCL-server's core. Localization minimizes cache misses. Each client-thread uses dedicated cache-line, which is used for critical section data storage and active waiting. This schema reduces access contention.

Fig 2. Remote Core Locking (RCL).

The current implementation of RCL has several drawbacks. At first there are no memory affinity in NUMA systems. Computer systems with non-uniform memory access (NUMA) (Fig. 3) currently are widespread. These systems are compositions of multi-core processors, each of which relates directly to the local segment of the global memory. Processor (group of processors) with the local memory constitutes a NUMA-node. Interconnection between processors and local memory addresses is made through the bus (AMD HyperTransport, Intel Quick Path Interconnect). The address to local memory is performed directly, the address to remote NUMA-nodes are more costly because of interprocessor bus. In multithreaded programs the latency of RCL-server addresses to the shared memory areas is essential for the execution time of a program. Memory allocation on the NUMA-node, which is not local to the node, on which RCL-server is running, leads to severe overheads when RCL-server addresses to the variables allocated on remote NUMA-nodes.

Fig 3. Structure of NUMA-systems.

RCL also has no mechanism of automatic selection of processor cores for server thread and working threads with considering the hierarchical structure of computer system and existing affinity. The processor affinity greatly affects on the overheads caused by localization of access to the global variables. Therefore user threads should be executed on the processors cores, located as more "close" to the processor

core of RCL-server. In the existing RCL implementation user have to choose processor core for the affinity of RCL-server and working threads by hands. Thus the tools for automation of this procedure is the actual problem.

This work propose the algorithm of RCL-locks initialization, which realizes memory affinity to the NUMA-nodes and RCL-server affinity to the processor cores, and the algorithm of sub-optimal affinity of working threads to the processor cores. The algorithms take into account the hierarchical structure of multi-core CS and non-uniform memory access in NUMA-systems to minimize critical sections execution time.

II. MULTI-CORE HIERARCHICAL COMPUTER SYSTEM MODEL

Let there is multi-core CS with shared memory, including N processor cores: $P = \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$. Computer system has hierarchical structure, which can be described as a tree, comprising L levels (Fig. 4). Each level of the system is represented by individual type of structural elements of CS (NUMA-nodes, processor cores and multilevel cache-memory). We introduce the notation: c_{lk} – the number of processor cores, owned by childs of an element $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, n_l\}$ from the level $l \in \{1, 2, \dots, L\}$; $r = p(l, k)$ – the first direct parent element $r \in \{1, 2, \dots, n_{l-1}\}$ for an element k , located on the level l ; m – the number of NUMA-nodes of multi-core CS; $j = m(i)$ – number $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$ of NUMA-node, containing a processor core i ; q_i – the set of processor cores, belonging to the NUMA-node i .

Fig 4. An example of hierarchical structure of multi-core CS $N = 8$, $L = 5$, $m = 2$, $c_{23} = 2$, $p(3; 4) = 2$, $m = 2$, $m(3) = 1$.

III. RCL OPTIMIZATION ALGORITHMS

For the memory affinity optimization and RCL-server processor affinity optimization we propose the algorithm RCLLockInitNUMA of initialization of RCL-lock (Fig. 5). The algorithm considers the non-uniform memory access and is performed during the initialization of RCL-lock.

On the first stage of the algorithm (lines 2-10) we compute the number of processor cores which is not busy by the RCL-server and the number of processor cores used on each of NUMA-node. Further (lines 12-18) we compute the summary number of NUMA-nodes with the RCL-servers. If there is only one such NUMA-node, we set the memory affinity to this node (lines 19-21).

The second stage of the algorithm (lines 23-34) includes the search of sub-optimal processor core and the affinity of RCL-server to it. If there is only one not busy by RCL-server processor core in the system, set the affinity of the RCL-server to the next already occupied processor core (lines 23-24). One

core is always free to run working threads on it. If there are more than one free processor core in the system, we search the least busy NUMA-node (line 26) and set the affinity of RCL-server to the first free core in this node (lines 27-32). The algorithm is finished by call of function of RCL-lock initialization with selected processor affinity.

```

1  /* Compute the number of free cores on CS and nodes. */
2  node_usage[1, ..., m] = 0
3  nb_free_cores = 0
4  for i = 1 to N do
5    if ISRCLSERVER(i) then
6      node_usage[m(i)] = node_usage[m(i)] + 1
7    else
8      nb_free_cores = nb_free_cores + 1
9  end if
10 end for
11 /* Try to set memory affinity to the NUMA-node. */
12 nb_busy_nodes = 0
13 for i = 0 to m do
14   if node_usage[i] > 0 then
15     nb_busy_nodes = nb_busy_nodes + 1
16     node = i
17   end if
18 end for
19 if nb_busy_nodes = 1 then
20   SETMEMBIND(node)
21 end if
22 /* Set the affinity of RCL-server. */
23 if nb_free_cores = 1 then
24   core = GETNEXTCORERR()
25 else
26   n = GETMOSTBUSYNODE(node_usage)
27   for i = 1 to q_n do
28     if not ISRCLSERVER(i) then
29       core = i
30     break
31   end if
32 end for
33 end if
34 RCLLOCKINITDEFAULT(core)

```

Fig. 5. Algorithm RCLLockInitNUMA.

For the optimization of working thread affinity we propose the heuristic algorithm RCLHierarchicalAffinity (Fig. 6). The algorithm takes into account hierarchical structure of multi-core CS to minimize the execution time of multithreaded programs with RCL. That algorithm is executed each time when parallel thread is created.

On the first stage of the algorithm (line 1) we check by the thread attributes if the thread is not RCL-server. For each of thread we search all the RCL-servers (lines 3-4) executed in the system. After that when first processor core with RCL-server is found, this core becomes the current element (lines 6-7) and we search the nearest free processor core for the affinity of created thread (lines 4-35). In the beginning of the algorithm processor core with no attached threads is the free core (line 5).

On the first stage of the core search we find first covering element of hierarchical structure. Covering element includes current element and contains more number of processor cores than it (lines 12-16). When the uppermost element of

hierarchical structure is reached we increment the minimal number of threads per one core (the free core now is the core with more number of attached threads) (lines 19-21). When the covering element is found we search first free processor core in it (lines 24-29) and set the affinity of created thread to it (line 32). Wherein for this core the number of threads executed on it is increased (line 33). After the affinity of the thread is set the algorithm is finished (line 34).

```

1  if ISREGULARTHREAD(thr_attr) then
2    core_usage[1, ..., N] = 0
3    for i = 1 to N do
4      if ISRCLSERVER(i) then
5        nthr_per_core = 0
6        l = L
7        k = i
8        core = 0
9        /* Search for the nearest processor core. */
10       do
11         /* Find the first covering parent element. */
12         do
13           clk_prev = clk
14           k = p(l, k)
15           l = l - 1
16         while clk = clk_prev or l = 1
17         /* When the root is reached, increase the minimal count
18           of threads per one core. */
19         if l = 1 then
20           nthr_per_core = nthr_per_core + 1
21           obj = i
22         else
23           /* Find the first least busy processor core. */
24           for j = 1 to clk do
25             if core_usage[j] ≤ nthr_per_core then
26               core = j
27             break
28           end if
29         end for
30       end if
31       while core = 0
32         SETAFFINITY(core, thr_attr)
33         core_usage[core] = core_usage[core] + 1
34       return
35     end if
36   end for
37 end if

```

Fig. 6. Algorithm RCLHierarchicalAffinity.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The experiments were conducted on the multi-core nodes of computer clusters Oak and Jet of multicenter computer system of Center of parallel computational technologies of Siberian state university of telecommunications and information sciences. The node of cluster Oak includes two quad-core processors Intel Xeon E5620 (2.4 GHz, sizes of cache-memory 1, 2 and 3 level correspondingly are 32 KiB, 256 KiB, 12 MiB) and 24 GiB of RAM. The ratio of rate of access to local and remote NUMA-nodes are 21 to 10. The node of cluster Jet is equipped by quad-core processor Intel Xeon E5420 (2.5 GHz, sizes of cache-memory 1 and 2 level correspondingly are 32 KiB, 12 MiB) and 8 GiB of RAM.

On the computing nodes the operating systems GNU/Linux CentOS 6 (Oak) and Fedora 21 (Jet) are installed. The compiler GCC 5.3.0 was used.

The synthetic benchmark was used in experiments. The benchmark performs iterative access to the elements of integer array of length $b = 5 \times 10^8$ elements inside the critical sections, organized by means of RCL. The number of operations $n = 10^8 / p$. As a pattern of the operation in the critical section we used the increment of a variable by 1. As the access patterns three patterns were used:

– sequential access: on each new iteration choose the element, following the previous one;

– strided access: on each new iteration choose the element with the index more by $s = 20$ than the previous one;

– random access: on each iteration randomly choose the element of the array.

Number p of parallel threads were varied from 2 to 7 (7 – number of not busy by RCL-server processor cores on the computing node) in the first experiment and from 2 to 100 in the second one.

The throughput $b = n / t$ of the structure was used as an indicator of efficiency (here t is time of benchmark execution).

We compared the efficiency of the algorithms of initialization of RCL-lock: RCLLockInitDefault (current RCL-lock initialization function) and RCLLockInitNUMA. Also we compared the affinity of the threads obtained by the algorithms RCLHierarchicalAffinity with other random arbitrary affinities.

In the experiments for RCL-locks initialization algorithms we used the thread affinity depicted on the Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Thread affinity to the processor cores in the experiments, $p = 2, \dots, 7$.

The Fig. 8 depicts the throughput b of critical section with number p of working threads. We can see that the algorithm RCLLockInitNUMA minimizes by 10-20% the throughput of critical section at random access to the elements of test array and at strided access. We can explain that by the fact that in these access patterns data is not cached in the local cache of processor core, on which RCL-server is running. Therefore RCL-server address to the RAM directly, wherein the access rate depends on data location in local or remote NUMA-node. The effect is perceptible at the number of threads comparable

to the number of processor cores (Fig. 8a, b), as like for greater number of threads (Fig. 8c) and significantly do not change when the number of threads is changing. The fixed affinity of threads to processor cores (Fig. 8a) is this case insignificantly affect to the throughput.

Fig. 8: Efficiency of the algorithms of RCL-lock initialization, cluster Oak. $a - p = 2, \dots, 7$, thread affinity in correspondence to 7, $b - p = 2, \dots, 7$, no thread affinity, $c - p = 2, \dots, 100$. 1 – RCLLockInitNUMA, sequential access, 2 – RCLLockInitDefault, sequential access, 3 – RCLLockInitNUMA, strided access, 4 – RCLLockInitDefault, strided access, 5 – RCLLockInitNUMA, random access, 6 – RCLLockInitDefault, random access.

The Fig. 9, 10 represent the experimental results of different affinities for the benchmark. The algorithm RCLHierarchicalAffinity significantly increases critical section throughput. The effect of the algorithms depends on number of threads (up to 2.4 times at $p = 2$, up to 2.2 times at $p = 3$, up to 1.3 times at $p = 4$, up to 1.2 times at $p = 5$ and an access pattern (up to 1.5 times at random access, up to 2.4 times at sequential access and up to 2.1 times at strided access).

Fig. 9: Threads affinity efficiency comparison, cluster Oak. $a - p = 2$, $b - p = 3$, $c - p = 4$, $d - p = 5$. \square – RCLLockInitDefault, random access, \blacksquare – RCLLockInitDefault, sequential access, \boxtimes – RCLLockInitDefault, strided access, \boxplus – RCLLockInitNUMA, random access, \boxminus – RCLLockInitNUMA, sequential access, \boxdot – RCLLockInitNUMA, strided access. $\bar{1}$ – working thread, \bar{RCL} – RCL-server, $\bar{\Delta}$ – thread allocating the memory.

Critical section throughput for benchmark execution on the node of cluster Jet (Fig. 10) insignificantly varies for different thread affinities. This is explained by the lack of shared (for processor cores of one processor) cache and uniform access to memory (SMP-system).

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The algorithms for optimization the execution of multithreaded programs based on Remote Core Locking (RCL) are developed. We proposed the algorithm RCLLockInitNUMA of initialization of RCL-lock with considering the non-uniform memory access in multi-core NUMA-systems and the algorithm RCLHierarchicalAffinity of sub-optimal thread affinity in hierarchical multi-core computer systems.

The algorithm RCLLockInitNUMA increases by 10-20% at the average the throughput of critical sections of parallel multithreaded programs based on RCL at random access and strided access to the elements of arrays on the NUMA multi-core systems. The optimization is reached by means of minimization of number of addresses to remote memory NUMA-segments. The algorithm RCLHierarchicalAffinity increases the throughput of critical section up to 1.2-2.4 times for all access templates on some computer systems. The algorithms realizes the affinity with considering all the hierarchical levels of multi-core computer systems.

Fig. 9: Threads affinity efficiency comparison, cluster Jet. $a - p = 2$, $b - p = 3$, $c - p = 4$, $d - p = 5$. – RCLLockInitDefault, random access, – RCLLockInitDefault, sequential access, – RCLLockInitDefault, strided access. – working thread, – RCL-server, – thread allocating the memory.

The developed algorithms are realized as a library and may be used to minimize existing multithreaded programs on base of RCL.

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